

IN-HABIT - INclusive Health And wellBeing In small and medium size ciTies

D8.7 COMMUNICATION ACTIONS REPORT II

Project Number	869227	Acronym	IN-HABIT
Full Title	INclusive Health And wellBeing In small and medium size ciTies		
Project URL	https://www.inhabit-h2020.eu/		
Document Type and Name	Deliverable, D8.7, Communication Actions Report II		
Project Coordinator	University of Cordoba		
Project Call and Funding Scheme	SC5-14-2019 - Visionary and integrated solutions to improve well-being and health in cities H2020-SC5-2019-2 (IA)		
Date of Delivery	M24 – Date 31/08/2022		
WP, WP Leader	WP8, BOT		
Status	Final		
Dissemination level (confidentiality)	Other/public/report		
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VERSION HISTORY

Version	Status	Date	Contributor/partner	Summary of changes
V 0.1	Draft	05/08/2022	BOT	Initial drafting
V 0.2	Revisions	24/08/2022	PPs, PC, LCREA	Final draft, peer reviewed
V 0.3	Final document	31/08/2022	BOT	Feedback included, language final revision

LIST OF ACRONYMS

D	Deliverable
DECO	Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication & Outreach
DC	Dissemination & Communication
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union

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GA	Grant Agreement
GDEI	Gender, Diversity, Equity, Inclusion
H2020	Horizon 2020 projects
IHW	Inclusive Health and Well-being
KLC	Key Local Contact
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
LCA	Local Community Activator
NBS	Nature Based Solutions
PC	Project Coordinator
PP	Project Partner
SMSCs	Small and medium-sized cities
T	Task
WP	Work Package

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable summarises the dissemination and communication activities related to project activities and results carried out by IN-HABIT partners during the last 12 months, M13 to M24 (September 2021-August 2022).

The structure of the document responds to the WP8 - Dissemination and Communication tasks distribution specified in the Description of Actions (DoA). The distribution of tasks is as follows:

T 8.1. Dissemination & Communication Strategy;

T 8.2. Communication & Engagement Actions and Tools;

T 8.3. Dissemination Actions and Tools.

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Deliverable description

Work Package 8 (WP8) is focused on the communication and dissemination of IN-HABIT goals and BOT, as communication leader, coordinates this task at a consortium level. To accomplish this objective, the first task to complete was to build a main communication strategy, which has been defined and shared with all partners and submitted in M6 (D 8.1, Dissemination and Communication Plan).

BOT monitors the frequency of general communication around the project, establishing a connection between general communication and local communication in the cities where the project is taking place, including the evolution in terms of dissemination, leading to the overall fulfilment of the objectives and the tasks defined in WP8.

To multiply the impact on the people involved and enlarge the community reached by this effort, IN-HABIT has developed an in-depth analysis of the interested stakeholders, including sister projects (clustering activities), related organisations, and local stakeholders, to engage them in the promotion of IN-HABIT's news and development. Hence, a wide and effective dissemination of results has been planned and identified as one of the project's main priorities to which all partners are committed to contributing.

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2. T 8.1. Dissemination & Communication Strategy

2.1. Year 2 general update

During the first year of the IN-HABIT timeline in WP8, a set of tools, methodologies, and communication flows addressing the external and internal audience was thoroughly selected and tailored to the context, considering the existence of a main objective and multiple secondary goals specifically defined according to different local, national, and European levels, diversity of targets, or the level of interaction sought. These activities have been implemented thoroughly, particularly focusing on public engagement and focusing on dissemination in Y2 of the project.

In particular, D 8.1. activities carried on from M12 included:

- Implementation of the Dissemination and communication plan;
- Continuous sharing of the Communication guidelines and updating tools by developing D 8.4 - City Communication Pack in December 2021;
- Adaptation of strategy to local contexts and necessities;
- Ad hoc training sessions on multiple subjects for the LCAs and KLCs;
- Dissemination actions - institutional and global outreach, focusing on the mapping and engagement of relevant stakeholders.

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All tools have been widely shared with Project Partners (PPs), considering suggestions and possibilities of amelioration whenever possible, through dedicated meetings and training, in order to foster inclusion and a collaborative, co-design approach that is key to the project.

2.2. Dissemination and communication plan (DECO) and Communication Guidelines

The DECO plan developed in M6 has been applied in Y2 to foster better communication among PPs (internal communication), with external stakeholders, and at a local level.

After the production of D 8.1, BOT, in collaboration with the rest of partners, now carefully monitors all aspects of the plan to perform quality communication of the project and its results, and has put in place specific measures to coordinate efficient internal communication among the project partners, including a focus on the implementation of outreach activities. The complete document is available on the IN-HABIT website, and shorter versions (video guides, guidelines, and manuals) have been shared with PPs for internal use, and with the member of their teams dedicated to communication activities: communication referents identified by PPs by M5 for each partner; Local Community Activators (LCA) and Key Local Contacts (KLC), identified in M6-M8 and playing an active role in communicating the project. A DECO plan addendum for the cities, tailor-made on local specific needs after collecting them in local training (M7) led by project partner Tesserae (TSR), was integrated with the GDEI Toolkit by M10 and is available for contributors for communication at IN-HUB level.

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Fig. 1 - DECO Plan objectives

In the meantime, gathering the needs of the PPs over the past few months, and in particular of the local IN-HUBS, some tools were optimised in order to offer user-friendly, easy-to-use repositories for data collection, referring to continuous actions of the project:

Communication repository for press and communication releases open to PPs.

General toolbox for PPs: a space dedicated to project communication where PPs can retrieve communication guidelines, visual identities, templates, and video guides.

Informative material:

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- project leaflet (initial version in 5 languages - local languages and English), to be used to present the project in meetings and to inform the general public. A more structured, extensive version will be made available after M24 when data and research baseline material will be ready to be included. The leaflet is available [here](#).
- project presentation: a general presentation for the general public, co-designed with all PPs (available [here](#)).

Communication guidelines were made available through the General Toolbox collaborative space.

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2.3. Local adaptations

During March and April 2022 (M19-M20) BOT organised specific communication workshops for KLCs, LCAs, and the local partners from each city in order to support them in the communication struggles they face on a daily basis, such as effectively reaching the different targets or producing video reports. Experts and professionals were involved in these workshops and will also be involved in the future.

BOT is also constantly mapping and observing the activities of all stakeholders both at an institutional and a local level, in cooperation with PPs, periodically monitoring the stakeholders on their digital communication channels: following their social media pages and visiting their websites on a weekly basis. Regular follow-up meetings with LCAs are currently being held every two weeks: this began in M7. Regular meetings to tackle challenges and exchange ideas with KLCs have also been held twice a month since M7. From Y2 on, these meetings have been optimised by holding a monthly meeting with LCAs and KLCs together, to identify possible transversal content, in particular for web and social media communications, and monthly one-to-one meetings with each city, to identify possible challenges and opportunities.

2.4. Communication Campaigns

A roadmap for the communication campaigns envisaged for the project was established and shared among the PPs in the Steering Committee and Assembly meetings. In particular, one

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general campaign (the presentation of the project) was accompanied by four local focused campaigns when the IN-HUBS were established.

The **general campaign**, postponed to September 2021 (M13) after consultation with the PPs and the PCoord, had the following characteristics: it focused on the project through an 'institutional storytelling' lens (objectives, values, PPs, evolution, results, description, research, links with global and European challenges, also based on joint activities IN-HABIT promotes in the institutional environment), and evaluated access of vulnerable groups and go digital in 2021 wherever outreach was possible due to the impact of COVID-19.

Within the general campaign, a **social media campaign** was launched in December 2021 (M16) with the involvement of transversal partners. In particular, research content was disseminated in collaboration with partner ISIM that issued an article on "IN-HABIT inclusive impact assessment" (published both on the project website and social media). Additionally, ISIM and BOT collaborated on the production of the section of the project website dedicated to the city surveys on health and well-being and on the local campaign to promote the city surveys through social networks, in collaboration with LCAs and KLCs.

Local campaigns in all cities were held from September to December 2021 with the following main purposes:

- Bring out local storytelling, practices, and results;
- Involve local groups, giving new spaces for communication, debate, and cooperation;
- Present best practices and results, in particular at a local level;
- Get public opinion and decision makers' attention.

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The following main focus points were addressed, mapping relevant activities both at a local and an institutional level:

Institutional

contents for the diary at a general level
 social coverage
 press coverage
 press review
 PP's storytelling
 Updates from the institutional environment
 Update from the scientific environment
 OUR FIRST EVENT - joint activity with sister projects

Fig. 2 - Institutional campaign setting

Local

Local storytelling
 social coverage
 local media coverage
 local groups storytelling
 Updates from the local environment and institutions in each cities
 Updates and best practices in the IN-HUBS

Fig. 3 - Local campaign setting

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2.5. Dissemination actions - institutional and global outreach

Ongoing dissemination actions include:

- Participating in NBS Task Force 4 on communication (joint strategies for communicating projects involving, among other objectives, nature based solutions);
- Mapping stakeholders and an institutional-relevant calendar for relevant ongoing initiatives;
- Participation in ongoing clustering activities with sister projects with the coordination of UCO to create synergies in communication and foster common actions.

A general strategy on how to address dissemination, and how to prioritise content and connections, was carried out starting from January 2022, becoming one of the main focuses of the project's communication and dissemination activities for the next two years. The general strategy has previously been discussed with the PC, and shared among PPs in various meetings on several occasions, in order to bring everyone's attention to this main purpose.

2.6. Press activity

A joint launch press release was issued by BOT at the beginning of the project (KoM, October 2020) in five languages and shared among all PPs. A press office activity was carried out to spread the news to relevant stakeholders shortly after and local partners were invited to do the same in their local communities.

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General Press Releases

Two general press releases were launched in the first two years of the project:

“New EU project pilots solutions to drive Inclusive Health and Well-being in Small and Medium Size cities”

“The IN-HABIT Project financed by the European Commission will transform four small and medium-sized cities into four innovative hubs of inclusive health and well-being”

Press Review 1 for the year 2020 and Press Review 2 for the year 2021 and the beginning of 2022, divided into general and the four cities, are also available in the Media and Press area of the website. A yearly report of communication activities is planned, with the first one having been delivered on the 31st of August 2021 (M12) (D 8.5 - Communication Actions Report I).

A press office activity has been started, including Press Office processes locally and at a general level, the preparation of a press kit and authorised contents, the organisation of translations and local content, the research for outputs and informative material, and finding out local channels used by institutions/service providers for primary information. A roadmap to support the four cities in the local launches has also been set up.

Up to the present time (M24), the project’s internal tracking tool shows the project has seen:

- 50 published news pieces locally from Cordoba (48 press or online articles, 2 TV reports)
- 19 published news pieces locally from Lucca (18 press or online articles, 1 radio report)

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- 5 published news pieces locally from Nitra (3 press or online articles, 2 TV reports)
- 10 published news pieces locally from Riga (9 press articles, 1 TV report)
- 13 general published news pieces (international)

Once the first wave of press conferences and dissemination events has been organised by partners, BOT will elaborate a summary report, merging the impact and hits of all the events as soon as the data is available.

Press launches and posts elaborated by each city partner

CORDOBA - 111 releases in Y2 of which:

- 12 on local, regional, and national radio programmes
- 34 posts on the IN-HABIT blog
- 15 articles on the UCO website
- 3 articles on the UCCI website
- 1 article on another website
- 48 in newspapers, magazines, and journals: 8 in the national press.
- 2 on regional television
- 13 on social media during an event with DFC

LUCCA - 54 releases in Y2 of which:

- 18 in newspapers
- 24 posts on social media pages
- 11 blog posts on websites

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- 1 on a radio programme

NITRA - 74 releases in Y2 of which:

- 57 posts on social media
- 12 online events (mainly at a local level)
- 3 press releases on websites
- 2 news pieces on the regional television

RIGA - 118 releases in Y2 of which:

- 61 posts on social media
- 17 posts on the IN-HABIT blog
- 25 blog posts on websites
- 6 online events
- 1 news piece on the national television
- 8 articles in newspapers

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3. T 8.2. Communication & Engagement Actions and Tools

3.1. Communication material and D 8.4 - City Communication Pack

On a first release, a short version of communication tools (leaflet) in local languages was developed and shared with PPs in M7 (March 2021), to be used in meetings and for local engagement purposes:

- 1 extended version in English published on the website and social media, helpful as a reference for general audiences;
- 4 reduced versions in local languages, personalised for the four cities.

Both versions are in pdf format and already ready for online use and print. BOT used an A4 format and special attention to colour and readability to print it or fold it very easily in case of a need to distribute it in meetings, even in black/white.

A project general presentation for general audiences has been completed with contribution of the PPs and is planned to be updated in Y3, in parallel with the increasing participation at conferences and events and focusing on research and innovation aspects of the project.

In general, infographics, imagery, and illustrations have been used to better convey important information, especially in online tools such as the website and videos communicating the first research results, planned for M25 onwards in cooperation with ISIMPACT.

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D 8.4 - City Communication Pack

The document includes all the available visual and digital tools, shared with the Local Community Activators of the participating cities and the Key Local Contacts in charge of communication actions. The tools have been developed after a thorough discussion with the above-mentioned teams, to guarantee they can be simply, easily, and effectively used during local communication and dissemination activities and events. An initial version of the D 8.4 - City Communication Pack was issued in December 2021 (M16), and is a living document that will evolve during the project's lifetime. In particular, as local communication initiatives are held, and communication necessities emerge, other specific tools will be added to the package and shared with the Project Partners. The package will be stored in the internal repository of IN-HABIT documents, ensuring access to all partners. The items contained in the pack have been designed following the suggestions and requests of LCAs and KLCs and all include: 1. specific layout instructions on how to print/produce such materials locally, 2. .ai versions, 3. editable .pdf versions, 4. printable layout characteristics (dimensions, materials, etc.) in order to be ready to produce project leaflets. An extended project leaflet is available in English (A4 format), and four locally focused leaflets (A4 format, foldable) are available in local languages on the website. Printable versions are available on the project internal repository as are Roll-ups, Stickers, Pins.

Further explorations

The virtual environment of the project is affected by the habits of use and access to different channels at different times of the day and in the lives of citizens. Local communicators,

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therefore, will have to be proactive in bringing the institutional communication of the project onto those channels used and disseminated at the local level, taking into consideration the different local targets.

3.2. Website

The IN-HABIT website is the main information showcase of the project. The IN-HABIT website's main structure has been defined and confirmed and comprises two parts:

- A public area to raise awareness and guarantee the visibility of the IN-HABIT project, as well as to encourage the participation of stakeholders and inhabitants through the publication of project updates and news and the promotion of local initiatives;
- A reserved area that only project partners will be able to access in order to share files and useful documents that might not be open access.

A **site map** can be found at: <https://www.inhabit-h2020.eu/site-map/>

The ultimate goal is to produce a multilingual, user-friendly, and easy-to-navigate space to enhance public awareness and promote local events, news, and results through a recognisable and strong visual identity based on the project's communication guidelines, as well as a recognisable dynamic space to disseminate project progress and results.

The website represents a multilingual modular communication platform whose purpose is to be used by city partners to promote local visionary and integrated solutions (VIS), by disseminating project updates, news, events, results, and products. The website will be

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integrated with the IN-HABIT platform and app and will embed social media news feeds throughout the project lifetime.

A totally new, significantly improved version of the website was developed and shared with PPs in July 2021, taking into account their suggestions through a collaborative and collated feedback approach. The new website also responds to the suggestions of the project advisor (PA) and European Commission for a more dynamic, yet clear vehicle of information and dissemination. The website can be reached at www.inhabit-h2020.eu and will be subject to regular updates as the project progresses. The website map has been designed to offer a complete overview of the project and easy access to all its activities. The website's main features are thoroughly described in D 8.3 (submitted in M6 for the landing page, and in M12 for the functioning website). This deliverable is available on the website itself.

Website efficiency is underpinned by the criteria of:

- Usability. Clear and accessible structure;
- Content updating;
- Accuracy in the content suitability.

The current website map structure has been designed as described more in depth in D 8.3, available on the website itself. A password protecting PPs' access to the Reserved Area of the website has also been developed. This area centralises the exchange of useful documents, not of public domain, among IN-HABIT PPs.

The priorities for Y2 of the website have been to focus on three main aspects:

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- SEO optimisation;
- Inclusion of articles of interest regarding innovation aspects of the project;
- Engagement of local IN-HUBs in content generation for local pages.

In order to improve the position of the website in search engine results and to improve the quality and quantity of the traffic, SEO activity has been necessary for all the website main pages. To update the cities' pages in this regard, it has been necessary to separate them into two different versions: one in the local language (which also appears in the menu) and one in English. The version in the local language is directed to the inhabitants of the city, features the blog section with news and events related to the project, and will occasionally be updated, while the version in English is for the general stakeholders and only contains a brief description of the actions planned for the area. The rest of the SEO (Search Engine Optimisation) actions won't be visible to the website viewers, all the pages will be indexed through the use of specific keywords that will help the website to appear in related web searches. In order to do so, WPs 1 to 4 participate in the task through the KLCs and specific training has been planned in Y3. The optimisation is a continuous process which will be implemented throughout the duration of the project.

Also, from Y3, a series of activities has been planned to implement public interest, related to the project values content section of the website. For this purpose, all PPs have been invited to share their suggestions for interesting content, and institutional or thematic repositories/newsletters/websites/social media are monitored by BOT to update the consortium and the public on topics of interest, i.e., sharing policy briefs, white papers, articles, and so on.

Analytics for the project website (Y2 - September 2021 to August 2022), can be found below.

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Unique visitors	General: 3797 Lucca: 71 Cordoba: 171 Nitra: 64 Riga: 55
Impressions	General: 65,300 Lucca: indexing ongoing Cordoba: 226 Nitra: indexing ongoing Riga: indexing ongoing
Visitors (geographic areas)	Spain: 31.47% USA: 20.06% Italy: 14.32%
Direct traffic	33.9 %
Organic traffic	36.3 %
Referral traffic	8.1%
Social traffic	21.7%
Recurrent visitors	85.7%
Traffic volume to 25/08/2022	Last week: 47 (+9.3%) Last month: 175 (-44.6%) Last six months: 1244
New visitors	14.3%

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Most visited pages	Homepage: 1391 Cordoba: 221 Project Partners: 168
Loading speed (time to interactive)	Desktop: 4s Mobile: up to 21s
Number of posts on local pages	Lucca: 7 Cordoba: 35 Nitra: 6 Riga: 18
Number of news articles on the website	25

Table 1 - Website analytics to M24

3.3. Social media and Storytelling

IN-HABIT Social Networks

Social media has become a very popular means of communication and disseminating information fast across heterogeneous target groups. These channels serve on-demand access to content anytime, anywhere, on any digital device. To extend the project target audience (especially to involve the general public and not only sector experts), IN-HABIT is integrating these media tools strategically in the communication and dissemination activities.

Twitter, LinkedIn, and Facebook have been selected as the most appropriate social networks to promote the project’s achievements, news, and outcomes so far. Instagram and Youtube will be added to the project accounts as soon as the communication training for KLCs and LCAs is

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completed, allowing every city to be an ambassador of their own progress, also in local languages. An editorial plan for internal use has been created. It contains the editorial strategy and the calendar of relevant events promoted by institutions, sister and clustering projects, and other Horizon 2020 projects that can be recalled in the IN-HABIT communication. The content is currently scheduled two weeks before publication. PPs were asked to participate in this process by mentioning relevant stakeholders and their channels, both globally and locally.

BOT, as a coordination leader, will act as a moderator of general social profiles, meaning controlling and filtering inadequate content, and monitoring the suitability and relevance of the information to be published.

Accounts

- Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/inhabith2020>
- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/68868676/admin/>
- Twitter: https://twitter.com/INHABIT_H2020

Official project hashtags have been shared, allowing the communication to be strengthened and different project aspects of the innovations carried out to be focused on, both at local and general levels:

- General: #Cityvolution #HumanSizeCity #INhabiTownns #innovatEU #EUinnovation
- Local: #EUforCordoba #EUforLucca #EUforNitra #EUforAgenskalns #CordobaInnovative #LuccaInnovative #AgenskalnsInnovative #NitraInnovative #CityShareCulture #CityGrowsFood #GreenNewCity #CityCareForPets

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| INSTAGRAM |
|--|---|--|---|
| 256 people follow the page | 262 people follow the page | 197 people follow the page | 123 people follow the page |
| 2-3 post a week
311 post in total (08/08) | 2-3 post a week
post in total (08/08) | 2-3 post a week
139 post in total (08/08) | 2-3 post a week
94 post in total (08/08) |
| Reach of people 2,325 | 3,225 Average of tweet impressions per month | Average of reactions per post 3,8 | Reach of people 8,398
380 profile visits |
| Organic engagement +14,9% in the last three months | 683 visits to the profile in the last 28 days | 865 Impressions per month | Organic engagement is 98 in the last three months |

Table 2 - Social media data up to M24

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Page and profile visits

Facebook Page visits 📊

488

Graphic 1 - Facebook page visits (Sep 21 - Aug 22)

Reach

Facebook Page reach 📊

2,325

Graphic 2 - Facebook page reach (Sep 21 - Aug 22)

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Graphic 3 - Instagram page visits (Sep 21 - Aug 22)

Graphic 4 - Instagram page reach (Sep 21 - Aug 22)

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Visitor metrics 🔍

Page views ▾
All pages ▾
All filters

Graphic 5 - LinkedIn page visitors (Sep 21 - Aug 22)

Tweet activity

📅 Sep 1 - Nov 30, 2021 ▾

📄 Export data ▾

Your Tweets earned **12.8K impressions** over this **91 day** period

Graphic 6 - Twitter impressions (Sep 21 - Nov 21)

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Tweet activity

Dec 1, 2021 – Mar 2, 2022

Export data

Your Tweets earned **14.9K impressions** over this **92 day** period

Graphic 7 - Twitter impressions (Dec 21 - Mar 22)

Your Tweets earned **7.0K impressions** over this **90 day** period

Graphic 8 - Twitter impressions (Mar 22 - Jun 22)

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Your Tweets earned **2.0K impressions** over this **39 day** period

Graphic 9 - Twitter impressions (Jun 22 - Aug 22)

Training webinars

In collaboration with the project partner TSR, dedicated webinars on communication and press activities were conducted for LCAs in May 2021. Specific meetings were planned and carried out from June and July 2021 on, as well as dedicated webinars, addressing all communication referents but in particular LCAs and KLCs, on:

- Promotional videos and highlights in cities to underline values and propositions;
- GDEI perspective with a practical approach with UREAD partner;
- Press, campaigning, and required training on actions involved in the local campaign.

Partners’ websites and social media

To date, all local partners have opened their channels on social media platforms, according to the degree of use in their local context of either one or another, and are connecting with local

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stakeholders and partners of the projects. These channels are in local languages and are managed by the KLCs and other IN-HUB participants. BOT, however, monitors and supports local communication according to the local teams' requests, and often re-posts and shares their content also in English on the official project pages, with the aim to promote concrete local innovations and activities and foster a sense of engagement and participation in a bigger community. Some partners have regular newsletters and regular posts on their own websites too, and all local PPs also support the updating of local communication and initiatives on the local pages of the IN-HABIT website. This continuous activity is currently used to disseminate the activities of the project regularly and frequently via these channels to complement the ongoing strategy.

IN-HABIT's local pages

Cordoba:

https://www.instagram.com/in_habit_cordoba/

<https://www.facebook.com/inhabith2020cordoba>

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/in-habit-h2020-uco-córdoba/>

https://twitter.com/in_uco

Nitra:

<https://www.facebook.com/InHubNitra>

Lucca:

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<https://www.instagram.com/inhabituca/>

<https://www.facebook.com/inhabit2020>

Riga:

<https://www.instagram.com/atirgus/>

<https://twitter.com/AgenskalnaT>

<https://www.facebook.com/Atirgus>

<https://www.facebook.com/InHabitRiga>

Storytelling and main planned activities

For each campaign, a Digital Editorial Plan is prepared and shared with all the components of the communication team. This tool contains all the content that will be shared in the next two/three weeks and provides a clear representation of the main campaign. The use of this tool will be shared during the Workshops, enabling KLCs to use it in order to increase productivity.

The social community is growing. Currently, IN-HABIT has 256 followers on Facebook, 236 followers on Twitter, 197 followers on LinkedIn, and 123 followers on Instagram. Content is being posted 2/3 times a week. The social media pages with the most interaction (not only in terms of likes but also impressions) are Facebook and Twitter with an average reach of 995 people per post on Facebook and 1,749 impressions per month on Twitter. On Instagram, the focus is also on maintaining a visually attractive feed, fundamental for the algorithm, by combining different types of content that captures the attention of the community. Fifty percent

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of the posts shared are around project content, while events, news, sister project content and European content makes up the remaining 50%.

- Mapping stakeholders, an institutional-relevant calendar for relevant initiatives, and promoting networking is ongoing and identified as a priority for 2022-2023, focusing on project awareness rather than on project results and data not yet available. Networking activities at an institutional level, in accordance with the UCO team, so that peer-to-peer relations might be established, has been identified as a priority for 2022.

- In particular: the PC was involved in an ongoing discussion on how to interact with high-level, international stakeholders, specifying the need to establish peer-to-peer relations first. BOT has been proactive, communicating relevant events and campaigns (such as MAKING CITIES EDIBLE, #HUGATREE by CLEARING HOUSE, URBAN GREEN UPs, NBS webinars, Cluster Task Force Meeting by NetworkNatureEU) and proposing or supporting the participation in institutional events/showcases (NEB - New European Bauhaus, Urban Green UP, Smart City Expo).

- Other activities to be implemented include: focusing on institutional and innovation content and guidelines to start conversations around topics relevant to the project (series of short interviews, webinars, etc.), creating an internal newsletter with highlights from the cities and transversal research partners.

In particular:

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- People campaign: short auto-recorded videos in which project participants, both from the cities and partners, present themselves and share their experiences. The campaign started in April 2022 and we will post one video per week.
- Quarterly newsletter: with the news from one city and a short focus on the activity of one partner. The first one was scheduled in March/April 2022.
- Webinars: with partners and referents of the sister projects. The aim of this activity is to discuss topics that are common between projects. These webinars are bimonthly and the first one is scheduled for April 2022.
- Editorials/interviews: opinions, thoughts, ideas about a specific topic. This content will be shared on the website. The frequency of posting will be one or two pieces per month.
- A mapping of relevant activities, both at a local and and institutional level, was displayed to the PPs and has been carried out.
- Thematic Planning for the year: a spreadsheet with a calendar form in which we underline important European matters and international days, anniversaries, and festivities. This enables the communication campaign, which lasts for two/four weeks, to be scheduled in advance and with a thematic relevance. This tool is public and can also be used by KLCs for their local activities.
- Dissemination of the project: the main aim is to communicate the project's purposes, phases, news, and impact. This is the most important activity on social media and is always linked to relevant matters, both European and international.

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- Disclosure of news about the IN-HABIT project areas of work: white papers, scientific articles, research about health and well-being in small and medium-sized cities.
- Promotion of events and initiatives: from the European environment, sister projects, and the four cities.
- Sharing and reposting: Content from the city pages is shared and reposted in order to increase the audience. The same activity is also carried out with content from sister projects if it is relevant for the IN-HABIT community.
- Workshop: during the communication workshop with the cities in M20-21 (April-May 2022), the relevant tools (Thematic Planning and Digital Editorial Plan) were shared with the audience and KLCs and they will be provided with all the information they need to use them. This will increase their autonomy and optimisation in digital communication while listening to the specific challenges encountered locally.

3.4. Promotional Video

The promotional video is acting, together with the website, as a window for the project. To better address the communication needs and targets, one promotional video about the project was produced in M10, and was combined with four short local teaser videos finalised in M12, produced using a co-design approach, sharing the scripts and suggestions from PPs, especially local ones. These videos in particular were used in the launch campaigns and are a powerful

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tool for local customised dissemination, also being subtitled in order to reach broader audiences locally.

Promotional videos are available on [the project website](#).

3.5. IN-HABIT App

The IN-HABIT APP will be extremely simple and therefore innovative in its ease of use: like a friendly fellow citizen. The app will geolocate the users, entrust them with a role (tourist, citizen, young explorer, administrator), and communicate the following to them (PUSH):

- content by spatial proximity (you're close to something that interests you and maybe you're not aware of it), or conveyed by QR codes dotted around the city (photograph and receive);
- content by temporal proximity (an event next week; a discount for something useful);
- communications about activities, discounts, and offers you're entitled to.

On the other hand, it will allow the user to communicate requests and report disservices etc. directly to the city administrations (PULL) and respond to surveys and/or behavioural games whose results and data (movement, activities, reading, consultation) on inhabitants' use of the city are delivered - in an anonymous form - to the administrators.

Discussion on initial technical requirements started with UCO and WTG partners in M5, following meetings with UREAD, ISIM, WTG, UCO, and LCREA partners between M6-M9 to understand in particular:

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- The aim of the app;
- Its application in correlation with the KPIs and needs expressed by the cities;
- Its feasibility in relation to the innovation actions undertaken in the cities.

The main features and interactions of the app were discussed, with the following steps undertaken: providing a list of functionalities for every city to choose from, combining them with missions to accomplish and rewards to be discussed, with the support of the referents for this task from each city; checking the compatibility and the best way to integrate the app with the IN-HABIT platform developed by WTG, in a dashboard, and other technical issues currently being addressed in smaller groups of discussion. Open discussion with relevant partners and participation in meetings with the cities' representatives on the matter is ongoing, with the help of a tailor-made UX guide and several meetings with experts. Current discussion and next steps involve the integration of the IN-HABIT app basic missions structure with the platform developed by WTG. The preliminary development was originally due in M22 (June 2022), postponed to M28 (December 2022), and a testing period in the cities will follow, up to the delivery of the final version in M36 (August 2023). A mockup of the app visuals has been developed and shared during the GAs, and is available on request.

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4. T 8.3. Dissemination Actions and Tools

4.1. Meetings, events, and digital approach

IN-HABIT partners collaborate in dissemination activities to their national and local audience, taking advantage of the close network they have in their own country. The IN-HABIT project was born in a year characterised by many changes that have revolutionised the uses, possibilities of communication and social interaction, and working methods, impacting the ability of some events to have a prominent offline participation capable of generating exchange, affection, interaction, and networking. The regulation resulting from the need to stem the COVID-19 pandemic has prevented demonstrations and events around the world from taking place, including the most important and symbolic ones. To date, it is not yet clear what will happen in the next year and if this will allow the project to return to previous meeting and communication habits. The unpredictability of events due to COVID-19 impacts the IN-HABIT project because it makes it more difficult to understand whether the physical events, which have objectives linked to the fundamental mission of the project (promoting inclusion, health and well-being), will be able to take place. In this phase of the project, however, it is important to be able to plan the organisation of such events also by evaluating the resources to be allocated that cannot be postponed.

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Events records from local IN-HUBs, Y2

CORDOBA: 74 local events starting from January 2022 (28 internal meetings, co-designs, and actions)

LUCCA: 1 event (22-21/02/2022) and one planned for November.

NITRA: 14 local events.

RIGA: 7 local events.

4.2. Institutional stakeholder relations and dissemination

As mentioned above, dissemination was identified as an area of primary focus from Y2 on. Accordingly, a strategy was shared with the PC and is currently being implemented and optimised whenever possible. It includes:

1. A General communication and Dissemination plan containing all actions ongoing or planned on various topics (press, social media, stakeholder relations, etc.). In most cases, they are really continuous tasks.

This file contains the event opportunities in detail to share with the PC or other partners for their evaluation and feedback, both for participation as speakers, showcasing the project, or simple dissemination. BOT plans to include this information also in the project newsletter.

Not all events have speaking opportunities, but they might be interesting from the point of view of institutional relations. Every two weeks, BOT maps all the events proposed by the European community, partners, sister projects, or general events in which everyone can be interested, so this can be considered a living document. Quick feedback is requested, in order to start planning, subscribing, and contacting the organisations behind the events. From then on, the PC can intervene to establish a very useful peer-to-peer relationship with fellow colleagues.

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2. Mapping stakeholders at various levels, to establish valuable connections and disseminate the IN-HABIT project or interesting content, etc. All partners, especially cities, and the PC, are kindly asked to keep this mapping updated, so BOT can build up opportunities from there.

4.3. Dissemination KPIs

Communication and outreach activities are monitored according to a set of quantitative and qualitative success indicators. The evaluation of communication activities determines the degree to which the communication objectives have been reached, and the relationship between the outcomes and the efforts made to reach the goals. This analysis helps the project to better understand facilitators and barriers of successful communication and serves to refine the communication activities accordingly. KPIs are currently in a phase of monitoring and revision, and dedicated follow-up is conducted among PPs to monitor progress (i.e. workshops, local events, local dissemination activities, etc.), taking into account the fact that many activities originally planned during Y1 have been postponed due to the pandemic situation and the consequent difficulties in selecting LCAs and the start-up of their activities.

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Fig. 3 - KPI scheme for IN-HABIT communication and dissemination

A set of KPIs has been specifically defined to monitor the successful deployment in terms of efficiency and effectiveness of dissemination activities. These indicators comprise:

Outputs/KPIs	Measurement Unit	Target Value	M24 KPIs
Project Website	-	1	1 - delivered
App published	-	1	ongoing
Project Visual Identity	-	1	1 - delivered
Project DECO strategy	-	1	1 - delivered
City communication pack	Number of items	4	1 - delivered
Policy guidelines for the replication of VIS that enhance IHW	-	1	

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Replicable Business Model to boost IHW	-	1	
Project brochure	Number of items	5	5 - delivered
Newsletters launched	Number of launches	50	4
Press launch	Number of launches	10	3
Launch about IN-HUBs established in each city	Number of launches	4	22 (12 Cordoba, 3 Lucca, 5 Nitra, 1 Riga)
Co-designed workshop designed in each city	Number of workshops	8	16 workshops organised (external) 4 training sessions and 5 workshops participated in (internal)
Business exploitation meetings	Number of business exploitation meetings	10	
Presentation Video	Number of videos	1	1 + 4 local - delivered
Video for local use	Number of clips	5	General: 90 Cordoba: 46 Lucca: 20 Nitra: 29 Riga: 21
Number of events attended as a guest	Number of events	10	
Number of events organised directly by the project (campaigns)	Number of events	5	5 (1 general campaign + 4 local campaigns)
Scientific publications	Number of mentions	10	
Resources shared (informative material)	Number of resources	25	5 leaflets (1+ 4 local) 1 general presentation 4 local presentations 42 articles/news pieces on website 14 articles/news pieces on website reserved area

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External audiences of the website	Unique visitors	30,000	(functioning website) 3,797 unique visitors, 65,300 impressions
Posts of dissemination on Facebook	Facebook Posts	500	140
Posts of dissemination on LinkedIn	LinkedIn posts	500	73
Tweets*	Number of tweets	100	192
Number on Facebook followers provided by the partners	Followers	3,000	62 (not sponsored, provided by social media management activity by BOT)
Press release articles published by media and detected in the press review	Clip Articles of press review	200	62 (see pg. 22)
Dissemination activities by partners	Activities/partner	5	Around 100 popularised publications (non scientific or peer-reviewed)
Local events provided by partners	Number of local events/partner	10	68 local events in all 4 cities
Activities of dissemination on IN-HABIT website on the city pages*	Number of blog posts	20	Total: 66 Cordoba: 35 Lucca: 7 Nitra: 6 Riga: 18
Number of events attended representing the project	Number of the events	10	21
New volunteers/city	Number of volunteers/city	10	About 80 for all the 4 cities (civil society)
Number of local causes actively supported	Number of causes	5	

Table 3 - IN-HABIT's communication KPIs up to M24

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Fig. 5 - IN-HABIT's KPIs in terms of public outreach, M18

4.4. Communication and dissemination Mid-Term and Final Reports

Four different reports are envisaged in T 8.3, every 12 months until the end of the project (M60), when a final report is planned. These reports summarise the work done in terms of communication and dissemination activities.

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